

DURABILITY OF ASPHALT BASED ON ALTERNATIVE ROAD BITUMEN

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Abstract. *The article highlights the technology for obtaining alternative road bitumen based on gossypol resin, oil sludge and waste diethanolamine. On the basis of alternative road bitumen, a method for preparing an asphalt concrete mixture was introduced. To evaluate the quality of the asphalt concrete mixture obtained on the basis of alternative road bitumen, experiments were carried out on such indicators as compressive strength, heat resistance, water resistance, water saturation, and positive results were obtained.*

Keywords: *gossypol resin, oil sludge, waste diethanolamine, alternative road bitumen and asphalt mix.*

Introduction. It is known that today the need for road bitumen used in asphalt production plants in the Republic of Uzbekistan is increasing day by day. Based on information from oil refineries and asphalt plants, raw material reserves are insufficient to provide 100 percent of road bitumen for asphalt production.

According to experts, one of the main factors affecting the long service life of asphalt concrete pavements is the use of high-quality petroleum bitumen. Organic binding material, which meets not only the quality indicators set by the current state standard, but also the operational reliability requirements of asphalt-concrete road structural layers created by their use. The evolution of the development of road construction in countries with a developed transport system, including the European Union, the United States, Canada, led to the understanding of the feasibility of the production and use of road bitumen from heavy upper layer oils of the naphthenic base in the middle of the 20th century, and the emergence of regulatory requirements for them [1-3].

When analyzing the research, many works were carried out on obtaining and developing road bitumen. In order to increase the amount of finished road bitumen and improve its quality, road bitumen compositions were obtained using rubber residues, polyethylene residues, oil and gas residues, oil industry residues and other modifiers [4-8].

Due to the scarcity of bitumen, many types of construction and road bitumen are purchased in large quantities from nearby countries. Due to the growing need for bitumen, we have developed a new recipe of alternative road bitumen based on the secondary products of the domestic oil and gas industry [9-10].

Research object and methods. Relying on the information from the scientific works of the above researchers, the results of research such as the composition, physicochemical properties, effects on humans and the environment of oil industry waste "Gossipol resin" and oil refining industry waste "Oil Sludge" were obtained, and to obtain alternative bitumen for us, it was appropriate to use it as a raw material.

Asphalt mixture preparation methodology. Asphalt concrete mixture preparation technology is carried out in the following order [11]:

- ready-made alternative road bitumen binder obtained on the basis of gossypol resin, oil sludge and used diethanolamine waste is heated and melted at a temperature of 130-140°C;
- a mixture of natural sand mixed with crushed granite pebbles and granite pebbles is heated;
- the solid phase is mixed with the prepared bitumen binder for 5-10 minutes;
- the prepared asphalt mixture is mass compacted at a pressure of 20 MPa with a holding time of 10 seconds.

In order to evaluate the quality of the obtained asphalt mixture, tests were conducted on parameters such as compressive strength limit, temperature resistance, water resistance, and water saturation.

Results obtained and discussion. The main goal of improving the quality of road bitumen binder is to improve the operational performance of asphalt concrete. The main purpose of choosing a brand of bitumen is explained by the fact that it is most often used in the asphalt-concrete mixture. In accordance with the requirements of GOST 12801-98 "Materials based on organic binders for road and airfield construction", we used alternative road bitumen binders obtained on the basis of gossypol resin, oil sludge, and diethanolamine waste for the preparation of hot asphalt concrete mixtures. The composition of the prepared asphalt-concrete mixture mass, %: fraction of granite pebbles and granite gravel mixture - 57 (5-17 mm); sand fraction (0-7 mm) - 35; mineral powder - 6; bitumen binder -8. Average density of samples - 2.16 g/cm³; average residual porosity of asphalt concrete is 4%. The composition and properties of asphalt concrete samples are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Properties of asphalt concrete samples obtained on the basis of alternative road bitumen

Content of bitumen binder in asphalt concrete, % mass.	Compressive strength limit at a temperature of 20 °C, R20, MPa	Compressive strength limit at 50°C, R50, MPa	Compressive strength at a temperature of 20°C after water saturation, P _{water} , MPa	Water resistance coefficient K _{water} = P _{water} / P ₂₀	Water saturation, W, %
BND 60/90	3,95	1,16	3,35	0,85	1,91
AB+M1	4,77	1,26	4,60	0,96	1,46
AB+M2	4,99	1,27	4,89	0,97	1,41
AB+M3	5,16	1,30	5,11	0,98	1,27
AB+M4	5,94	2,03	5,83	0,97	0,95
AB+M5	5,75	1,85	5,25	0,96	1,11
AB+M6	5,61	1,70	5,11	0,95	1,18

Note: AB- alternative bitumen; M1- modifier (used diethanolamine waste) -3% mass; M2- modifier (used diethanolamine waste) -5% mass; M3- modifier (used diethanolamine waste) -7% mass; M4- modifier (used diethanolamine waste) -9% mass; M5- modifier (used diethanolamine waste) -11% mass; M6- modifier (used diethanolamine waste) -13% mass;

As can be seen from the table, with an increase in the amount of the modifier (GQ+NSH+IDEA), the strength of the asphalt concrete increases, while the water saturation index decreases, this alternative way is explained by the increase in the adhesion of bitumen to the mineral material. When working under a certain local load, the main attention should be paid to

asphaltene aggregates, if it exceeds certain local loads, it is observed that the main force is occupied by the maltene fraction, because then it starts to move to easily mobile molecules, and the asphaltene aggregates begin to move in the mass of maltenes, which leads to the deformation of asphalt concrete samples. Gossypol resin, petroleum slurry and used diethanolamine strengthen the working system of the bitumen, thereby helping to distribute loads over a large volume of material. This leads to an increase in the viscosity of the bitumen binder, that is, to an increase in the strength of the mineral material based on it.

Conclusion. After conducting the tests, we came to the following conclusion, in the case of an alternative road bitumen recipe (gossypol resin + oil slurry + used diethanolamine), it leads to an increase in the strength indicators of asphalt concrete mixture samples, that is, it increases the compressive strength by 1.7 times compared to oil-derived bitumen, and reduces the water saturation index. From the point of view of strength indicators, sample AB+M4 should be considered optimal for the preparation of asphalt concrete mixture when the amount of gossypol resin in the alternative bitumen binder is 75% by mass, the amount of oil slurry is 25% by mass, and the amount of diethanolamine used is 9%.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Decree No. UP-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic".
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Resolution PP 3262 of September 11, 2017 "On measures to improve the system of landscaping and architectural and landscape design of highways".
3. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Decree No. UP-4954 of February 14, 2017 "On measures to further improve the road management system".
4. Negmatov S.S., Dzhumbayev A.B., Ablokulov A.A., Inoyatov K.M. New promising technology for the use of minerals in asphalt concrete pavements of highways. // Composite materials. - Tashkent, 2004. No. 4. -P. 49.
5. Rosenthal D.A., Syroezhko A.M. Changes in the properties of road bitumen upon contact with mineral filler // Chemistry and technology of fuels and oils. 2000. No. 4. P. 41-43.
6. Emelyanycheva E.A. Modification of road bitumen with polymer and organomineral additives. Abstract of the Cand. Tech. Sciences. - Kazan. 2011. -23 p.
7. Pokonova Yu.V. Oil bitumen / Yu.V. Pokonova. - SPb.: St. Petersburg publishing company "Sintez", 2005.- 154 p.
8. Khamidov B.N., Fozilov S.F., Saidakhmedov Sh.M., Mavlonov B.A. Oil and gas kimyosi. Ohkuv kullanna. T.: Muharrir nashriyoti, 2014-582 b.
9. Khamidov Basit, Rakhimov Bekzod, Musayev Marufjan, Rakhmatova Dilnoza. Obtaining a new composition of road bitumen from local waste of oil-gas and oil-fat production. International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology Vol. 8, Issue 9, September 2021.
10. Khamidov Basit, Rakhimov Bekzod, Musayev Marufjan, Rakhmatova Dilnoza. Comparative Tests of Experimental Batches of a New Composition of Road Bitumen. International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology Vol. 8, Issue 9 , September 2021.
11. Prokopets V.S. Asphalt concretes based on porous fillers of Western and Eastern Siberia /V.S. Prokopets, V.D. Galdina, G.A. Podrez // Construction materials. - 2009. - No. 11. - P. 26-28.